

HARMONY OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION, AESTHETIC CONSCIOUSNESS, AESTHETIC CULTURE AND EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT.

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Abstract: Aesthetic education first of all develops a person's ability to perceive, understand and value beauty in reality and art. Aesthetic education also stems from the need to create aesthetic wealth in any field of human activity, that is, to create according to the law of beauty. Aesthetic education depends on social conditions. The main goal of aesthetic education is to help the members of the society to fully feel the beauty for all-round perfect development.

Keywords: Aesthetic education, aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic culture, education, creativity.

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Vital factors of aesthetic education are not only aesthetics, culture, art, and literature. In addition to the manifestations of social consciousness and aesthetic views, economic and political relations, life and technology, sports and national traditions are extremely important factors in the education of sophistication. Without fully implementing aesthetic education, a well-rounded person developed on the basis of moral, ideological and political education cannot be brought to adulthood. The main meaning and task of aesthetic education is to help people develop their feelings, imagination and thoughts about the beauty of the world in a comprehensive and harmonious way.

Aesthetic education, first of all, consists in educating the ability to see beauty in nature and society, as well as in works of art, to understand and appreciate it correctly. It means cultivating the ability to give beauty to all aspects of life and work, fighting against absurdity and ugliness in life and art, and showing one's creative perfection in art depending on one's ability. The real essence of aesthetic education is to teach a person to correctly perceive the beauty that exists in the real world and to fight for real beauty in life. The following conclusions can be drawn from the above:

First of all, as a result of his work, a person aesthetically assimilates reality. He discovers and perceives the beauty in it. Secondly, all methods and tools of aesthetic education work should be focused on the development of correct aesthetic thinking and perception in a person. That is, a person's aesthetic assessment, judgment and perception should correctly reflect the beauty or ugliness that exists

in reality. Thirdly, aesthetic education implies the development of all-round and broad aesthetic tastes and interests in a person, educating people in the spirit of creating beauty and looking at all ugliness and ugliness with contempt.

The goal of aesthetics is to educate and develop a person's ability to perceive and evaluate beauty in life and art from the point of view of universal values. We mean a perfect person who adds to the beauty of life with his work, who raises his work and social activities to the level of aesthetic perfection. "If a man's spouse does not make him wise, no wise man should bother to teach him words, and his work will be wasted," says Kaikovus.

Therefore, the role of life influence in the education of a person did not escape the attention of Kaikovus. He also considers education to be one of the factors that shape the human mind and personal life. According to him, the purpose of knowing the world is to use it. Simple music, beautiful flowers, pictures create an initial aesthetic experience. Aesthetic education of pre-school and school-age children is primarily aimed at forming their ability to "see", "hear", distinguish and evaluate the beauty of nature and the environment. For this, singing, playing music, drawing, and making figurines are widely used. Aesthetic education is inextricably linked with mental, moral, ecological and physical education. Aesthetic education plays an important role in forming the moral culture of the young generation. Cultivating the need for art, its understanding, and the desire to actively participate in artistic creation is the primary task of aesthetic education. Art, on the other hand, is an important means of aesthetic education aimed at a certain goal. Aesthetic feeling appears in the process of aesthetic perception of life events or works of art. Aesthetic feeling consists of a unique experience created by this perception, which occurs as a feeling of beauty and sublimity, tragedy or fun. A person's aesthetic attitude to life is a product of historical development. It reflects the level of aesthetic consciousness of society.

Aesthetic education, like other forms of education, focuses its attention on an individual and a social group. Aesthetic education serves to determine universal and national values. It is clear that education has the goal and task of influencing the human mind, emotions, imagination, beliefs, worldview, actions, behavior. Aesthetic education acts as a component of this general goal and task, and represents a socially significant event. It should be noted that in the ancient world, the purpose of education in general was manifested on an aesthetic basis. For example, in the ancient Greeks, the goal of aesthetic education was aimed at the all-round development of citizens, finding the harmony of "spirit and body".

In the teachings of great thinkers such as Plato and Aristotle, the system of aesthetic education has different aspects, but there is also a commonality. Today, the importance of aesthetic education is increasing. First of all, in the conditions of independence, the human factor is increasing, and the noble qualities,

consciousness, activity, and creative abilities of people working in all aspects of life are growing. Secondly, in the process of increasing the general culture of the majority of the population of Uzbekistan, the work of organizing the production of new equipment and technologies is becoming more and more perfect. Thirdly, new production relations, market economy taking a wide place, and further development and implementation of the law require an increase in the general culture of citizens, especially aesthetic culture. Fourthly, in the conditions of the scientific and technical revolution, such sciences as electronics, automatics, cybernetics, informatics create opportunities for radical restructuring of the production sector. This situation calls for a fundamental change in the mental state of people engaged in production, as well as an increase in their social, spiritual, and moral aesthetic level. Fifthly, as a result of the widespread use of mass media such as radio, the press, and especially "mirror of the world", the volume of artistic information has increased dramatically, requiring more attention to aesthetic education.

REFERENCES:

1. B. S. Siddiqov, & sh. N. Mexmonaliyev (2022). Pedagogik amaliyotning bo'lajak o'qituvchining kasbiy tayyorgarlik faoliyatida tutgan o'rni. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (1), 10-16. Doi: 10.24412/2181-1385-2022-1-10-16
2. MAZMUNI, T. M. A. J. V. Sh. N. Mexmonaliyev–Farg ‘ona davlat universiteti 2-bosqich magistranti SS Evatov–Farg ‘ona davlat universiteti o‘qituvchisi OA Tursunov–Farg ‘ona politexnika instituti akademik litsey o‘quvchisi. FARG ‘ONA DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI, 275.
3. Khaitboevich, B.B. (2020). Some features of protection of students from the threat of harmful information in the educational process. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8 (10), Part II, 69-72. <http://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Full-Paper-some-features-of-protection-of-students-from-the-threat-of-harmful.pdf>
4. Baydjanov, B. (2021). Compatibility of new renaissance pedagogy and jadid enlighteners' views on education and information security. International peer-reviewed online conference on theme: "Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy and the press of jadids". (1). <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.916>
5. Siddikov, B. S. "THE IMPORTANCE OF SPORTS AND RECREATION ACTIVITIES FOR A HARMONIOUSLY DEVELOPED GENERATION." Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества. 2020. 5.

6. Tuychieva, Inoyatkhon I. "Mechanisms Ensuring Children's Thought Activity Development at Preschool Education Process." *Eastern European Scientific Journal* 6 (2018). 7.
7. Jalalov, Bakhromjon Bekmurzaevich, H. A. Khatamov, and F. U. Na saidenova. "Advantages of collective learning." *Scientist of the XXI century* (2016)
8. Jahongir Umidjon O'G'Li Tojiboyev (2022). TALABALARDA ESTETIK MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3 (1), 585-594. doi:10.24412/2181-1385-2022-1-585-594
9. SAIDKULOVICH, S.B., & UGLI, T. J. U. The Social Pedagogical Necessity of Developing Students' Aesthetic Culture in the Process of Globalization. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 8(1), 75-77.
10. Umidjon o'g'li, T. J. (2022, November). KREATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARNING ESTETIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 42-44).